

A Literature Review on Library and Information Science with Focus on Non-Academic Libraries

Dr. Sonali Saha¹, Mangesh Ohal², Varshita Jetwani³

¹Associate Professor, Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Pune, Maharashtra, India

²Librarian, Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Pune, Maharashtra, India

³Student, Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Pune, Maharashtra, India

ABSTRACT

The literature on Library and Information Science LIS is widely available. However, in terms of application, the literature is tilted towards academic libraries. On the other hand, the research on the application in non-academic libraries is limited. Yet, the two applications are not altogether different. There are characteristics of an academic library that are relevant for a non-academic library as well. But non-academic libraries have their unique features. Exhaustive research is available in the area of academic libraries. Researchers, in particular, have highlighted IT related topics given the developments in IT. Surprisingly, attempts to seek expansion or extension from academic libraries to other libraries have not been researched much. While depth in the single line of academic libraries is quite evident, bit horizontal dimensions do not seem to have attracted researchers much. The gap is quite evident. This paper carries a literature review with a comparative perspective of research in the two types of libraries.

Keywords: Academic libraries, non-academic libraries, LIS

INTRODUCTION

There has been tremendous growth of digital information resources and services and huge amounts for acquiring such information resources and rendering various types of digital information services. However, as has been seen in various literature, the main emphasis has been given on the academic libraries, and very little or rather no work has been done concerning the non-academic libraries, which are gaining a place of importance in today's changing world of Information Technology. This paper carries a literature review with a comparative perspective of research in the two types of libraries.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

LIS in general and in academic libraries

Tait, Martzoukou, and Reid (2016) have evaluated IT utilities' role in the transformation of academic library services. In conclusion, the authors have said that within the rapidly changing environment of academia, there are not only new emerging roles for academic library staff (for example, research and data management) but also orthodox roles (for example, information literacy instruction) that have evolved with greater demands placed on technological, interpersonal, IT and transferable skills. The evolution of the subject domain expertise within multidisciplinary research fields and the world of academic information has become increasingly more complex with open access, big data, and new models of online learning, teaching, and research (for example, blended learning, online research) will likely lead to further challenges and opportunities in future.

SCONUL, (2015), in its publication on e-books, has found out that the increasing student numbers at higher education institutions mean that the footfall in academic libraries has increased, although user behavior, including borrowing patterns, have changed significantly over the last ten years. It further states that there has also been a shift in the user demographics of academic libraries and changes in how patrons engage with the physical space.

Cameron and Siddall, (2015) have carried a study of Talis Aspire and reading lists and have highlighted the need to improve communication between faculty and library staff needs drawing from earlier research that identified an "asymmetrical disconnection" (Christiansen et al., 2004: 18) between academics and library staff with the former having little understanding of the responsibilities and roles of library staff in setting up and managing these lists.

Datig (2015) has put forward a view that libraries have responded to the new challenges by developing new methodologies for analyzing user experiences (sometimes known as "UX research") that include qualitative

ethnographic studies to understand better how patrons use library spaces. Quoting observational studies by researchers such as Applegate (2009), the authors have demonstrated that while students are using academic library spaces in different ways than before (for example, bringing their laptops), that the library continues to be a key space for learning and scholarly activities within academic institutions and that effective libraries must be responsive to these needs.

Kingsley and Kennan (2015), discussing open access, have stated that it is a global phenomenon and have identified initiatives in a range of countries, including the United States, where open access has been mandated for funding recipients from the National Institutes of Health since 2007.

RCUK (2015), in its policy announcement, has said that in the United Kingdom, funding councils have introduced requirements for academic institutions to have formal processes in place for curating data generated by publicly funded research projects. Research data is a resource that demands sophisticated approaches to curation and management (as Joint Information Services Commission (JISC) has identified in its Managing Research Data Programme 2011–2013)

Sahu, Goswami, Choudhury (2014) highlighted the R&D information needs of scientists, engineers, managers, and researchers in metallurgy working in selective metallurgical institutions in Jharkhand, India. The study revealed that the R&D groups of these organizations used various formal and informal information sources effectively in meeting their research information needs. Apart from the literature search, the teams attend meetings, discussions, seminars, workshops, and conferences as the major informal sources of acquiring knowledge, sharing experiences with their colleagues and experts, and establishing professional contacts to exchange knowledge. Government-funded organizations have a regular budget to support their knowledge resources, whereas public-funded organizations are mostly project-based funding and fluctuate from time to time as also in the case of privately funded, which are mostly need-based. Similar is the case for document procurement services and knowledge sharing in all three kinds of metallurgical organizations.

Walters (2013), in his article "Libraries and the academy," has observed that beyond the challenges encountered, this is another area that library staff is allowed to define and assert new and significant roles. The author has emphasized that academic library staff are well-positioned to offer guidance to eBook vendors for the development of meaningful e-book licenses and usable platforms for the academic environment, and this implies that they "have an important role to play in shaping the e-book environment, especially since publishers have yet to agree on the best ways of providing and marketing e-books to academic libraries."

National Literacy Trust (2013) has published results of a survey of almost 35,000 8- to 16-year-olds, claiming that young people are now much more likely to prefer to read on a computer screen rather than a printed book or magazine, which makes sense considering that 85 percent have a mobile phone while only 73 percent own books (Clark and Hawkins, 2010).

Egunjobi, Taofiq, and OlufelaI (2013) investigated the carrier choices and the academic profile of LIS professionals. The study also examines the LIS education in Nigerian Universities. They recommend sustained and continuous awareness about LIS to ascertain that LIS schools are not dumping ground for low intelligent quotient undergraduates.

Muralidhar and Rao (2013) discussed public-private partnership (PPP) and examined how it is different from the 'privatization' concept. It examined the present status of public libraries in India and the need for mobilizing support for their improvement. The authors stress the need for implementing the National Knowledge Commission recommendation for PPP. The paper highlighted the public sector and private firms' role in developing public libraries through the PPP model. In the end, suggestions were made on implementing the model for the development of public libraries.

Horava and Curran (2012), in their work, mentioned that as the curriculum and methods of LIS education are evolving to meet new expectations, the case study methodology is an important pedagogical tool to strengthen the skills of students. The educational theory of John Dewey and the management theory of Henry Mintzberg provide the foundational context. There is significant value in this methodology regarding adult learning characteristics such as active learning and incorporation of the student's life experience in problem-solving and scenario analysis. As referenced in the statements of various professional associations such as the ALA and SLA, the core competencies expected of librarians can be developed during the LIS education by utilizing this approach. At the University of Ottawa, where the authors teach, the School of Information Studies has defined its learning outcomes. It is clear that the case study approach aligns very closely with these outcomes and is, therefore, an excellent method for enhancing the program's quality.

Goswami and Biswas (2011) examined that information technologies are rapidly changing in the modern information era in all aspects. Now the digital resources are readily available from many sources, and those contents are available

by the teachers and learners through the Internet. For that reason, a movement aims to encourage and enable sharing content freely called Open Educational Resources. Several libraries and library consortiums have taken the forefoot in producing resources for all. Librarians, whose ranks are filled with specialists and experts in various fields, can be contributors to the open educational commons by creating OERs themselves. India is becoming an active player in the open-source software movement and the Open Access (OA) movement, and the Open Educational Resources movement. By this OERs and open educational movement, the resourceful librarian with vision, who stays abreast and remains open to the changing trends in the educational world, who is knowledgeable of available resources both print and online, and who becomes an essential partner in the collaborative educational efforts of both instructor and student.

Thomas, V.K., Satpathi, C and Satpathi, J.N. (2010) found that the modern academic librarian, besides the common attributes, should be technology-savvy and eager to learn and adopt any technology development for the benefit of users. Regular updating of professionals is the sine qua non. In the Indian context, it is found that professional bodies like IASLIC did play a yeoman's role in bringing India to the forefront of global librarianship. It is concluded that India needs a well-laid out policy and programs of updating and equipping its librarians continuously and can benefit from ALA and CILIP.

Siddamalliah and Kemparaj (2006) call this type of curriculum design based on the inputs from published material, case studies, and best practices the Traditional Model and Lorrington (2004) identifies it as the Professional – School Model in which he depicts that the library-oriented professionals extract the different subject from the library context.

Varalakshmi (2006) the research study results based on opinions regarding the curriculum of one university apply to other parts of the country as the syllabus is based on the UGC Model Curriculum, which most universities have adopted. The professionals who responded are from various parts of the country. Therefore the interpretations made and suggestions deduced may help other LIS institutions as well. To make tomorrow's workforce competitive in an increasingly high-tech world, imparting and learning ICT skills must be priorities. However, the academician's view is that they should not cloud the basic professional concepts and influence the curriculum negatively. But the library professionals do not seem to be happy with the outcome of library schools as indicated by the study and believe that preparing students for the future does involve teaching them technology skills, soft skills, and management skills. The study also indicated that the LIS departments in developing countries are being affected by unresolved issues such as identity and sustainability crises, the proliferation of institutions, sharp decline in applicants, average score points of entrants, scarcity of financial resources, and low salaries offered to new professionals.

The departments have to overcome such limitations and work towards excellence. The study indicates that the existing programs are not excellent given the products and the market. As in the developed countries, I-schools may be developed as has already been introduced by the Department of Library and Information Science, University of Mysore. The author has mentioned some viable alternates for LIS departments in India, and other developing countries are to offer the program at different levels to meet the diversified demands of the information market. Indeed, today's challenging economic situation means that it is no longer sufficient for a new graduate to know an academic subject; increasingly, students must gain those skills that will enhance their employment prospects. Employability skills include handling and retrieving information in any format, communication and presentation, planning and problem solving, and social development and interaction. The author has suggested that LIS curricula should reflect these features.

Perrault et al. (2002) present a case study in which it was used in the LIS domain. Bloom (1956) proposed that learning occurs in three domains: affective (growth in feelings or emotional areas), cognitive (mental skills), and psychomotor (manual or physical skills).

Judith and Hayward (2000) clearly described that information managers/professionals' role is in a state of transition within the UK financial services sector. The term 'information professional' was recognized in retail banks; it was associated with roles and responsibilities far beyond a set of traditional search and retrieval skills.

Tchobanoff and Price (1998) described the qualities they look for in library school graduates to fill positions in their organizations and the key skills they expect to be included in library schools' curricula. Library employers are consumers of library school products and library schools should be aware of their consumers' needs. Special libraries have special requirements and subject specialization, such as determining the priority of requests, appreciating the impact of information on the business, and the timeliness of replies to the requests. Simultaneously, they are often small departments where each member must be a generalist, and there is not much time to take on outside duties. Nevertheless, they recommend several steps that special librarians can take to bring special library concerns and needs to the formal education program.

Wijetunge (1998) The empirical survey identified that six main subjects are taught across most of the LIS programs; that most programs provide general knowledge in LIS but not opportunities for specialization; appropriate levels of

complexity were not evident across the different levels of programs, and there is no national core in LIS so that all programs cover a set of common subjects at appropriate depths and breadths suitable for different levels of programs. Findings of the curriculum development strategies identified that most of the curricula documents are not comprehensive and that the Sri Lankan LIS curriculum developers do not use any formal curriculum development model. Analysis of the curriculum development teams indicated that most members have no curriculum design training, and the teams lack contributions by other stakeholders except LIS professionals. Several recommendations are presented to eliminate the weaknesses of the curriculum development strategy in the LIS programs.

In his thesis, Singh (1991) explained: "The Internet and Special Librarians: Use, Training and the Future," which focuses on Corporate Special Librarians using the Internet in a for-profit setting. Through a survey method, it seeks to establish who are the Internet users, which resources are being used most, who provides the training, what is most exciting and most frustrating about using the Internet, and to predict, based on their experiences, the future of the networked library/information centers with the Internet as an important reference and research tool. This exploratory study found that corporate librarians are very aware of the serious consequences of not integrating the resources available on the Internet in their routine library work and are enthusiastically exploring the new frontiers of "cyber-space" on their way to becoming expert "Cyber- The International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA) in 1927, is concerned with the problems raised by the library education. In 2000, IFLA Section on Education and Training published *Guidelines for Library/Information Professional Programs*. This document provides a large framework for developing and evaluating universities, their curricula, and personnel, students, administration, budgets, educational resources, etc.

Many professional associations have come up with a recommended core for LIS education programs. The American Library Association (ALA) prepared a draft core with eight competencies (McKinney, 2006). Chartered Institute of Library and Information Professionals (CILIP) of the UK has presented a core to which they refer as the Body of Professional Knowledge (BPK) (CILIP, 2007). BPK describes the specialist subject knowledge, which distinguishes LIS staff from those who work in other information professions. Australian Library and Information Association (ALIA, 2005) has identified a set of core knowledge aspects and generic skills and attitudes that the contemporary LIS professionals should possess.

LIS in non-academic libraries

Wainwright, Amy, and Davidson, Chris (2017), in their work "Academic Libraries and Non-Academic Departments: A Survey and Case Studies on Liaising Outside the Box," published in *Collaborative Librarianship*, have concluded that academic librarians of all sizes reported that they are partnering consistently with non-academic departments. Regularly, librarians express these partnerships' value, reporting advantages like better campus relationships, a wider understanding of library services, and more promotional opportunities. These relationships are often low-cost for the library and end up benefitting all parties involved. In the light of several advantages, the authors have recommended that library administrators should consider formalizing these roles in their strategic efforts to raise the library's profile on campus and reach users that they are not reaching through traditional means.

Ahmed, Waqar; Soroya, Muhammad Shahid (2016), in their work titled "Library and information science education as an ignition source for services in special non-academic libraries," have carried a study on LIS application in special non-academic libraries in Pakistan. It was found that the professionally qualified library managers were better at providing librarians' end services. The study, a first of its kind in Pakistan, depicted the electronic, librarians' end, technical knowledge, and multi-factor services and measured its variation on the educational grounds.

Fredrik Astrom (2006), in his doctoral thesis "The Social and Intellectual Development of Library and Information Science," has observed that many fields have application-oriented research and strong connections to non-academic fields, even if the fields were traditionally considered 'pure' sciences suggesting that LIS might not be an exception to this.

CONCLUSION

Exhaustive research is available in the area of academic libraries. Researchers, in particular, have highlighted IT related topics given the developments in IT. Surprisingly, attempts to seek expansion or extension from academic libraries to other libraries have not been researched much. While depth in the single line of academic libraries is quite evident, bit horizontal dimensions do not seem to have attracted researchers much. The gap is quite evident. The profession can seek entry in non-academic domains, how its professional approach can be useful, changes in the curriculum, and other such aspects have not been researched. More research in this area is certainly warranted.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Ahmed, Waqar; Soroya, Muhammad Shahid, 2016, Library and information science education as ignition source for services in non-academic special libraries, *Library Review*; Glasgow, Emerald Group Publishing Limited, Volume: 65, Issue: 4/5, Pages: 350-368
- [2]. Cameron C and Siddall G (2015) *Academic staff perceptions and use of reading lists for book ordering. SCONUL Focus*; 64, 41–44.
- [3]. Dasgupta, A. and Satpathi, J.N. (Eds) (2007). IASLIC: Challenges and Prospects”, Indian Association of Special Libraries & Information Centres. Kolkata
- [4]. Datig I (2015) *Walking in your users’ shoes: an introduction to user experience research as a tool for developing user-centered libraries. College & Undergraduate Libraries*; 22 (3-4): 234–246.
- [5]. Egunjobi, A. F., Salisu, T. M. and Ogunkeya, O. (2013). Academic profile and career choice of fresh undergraduates of library and information science in a ‘Nigerian University of Education. *Annals of Library and Information Studies*, vol. 60, p. 296–303, Dec. 2013.
- [6]. Fredrik Astrom (2006), “The Social and Intellectual Development of Library and Information Science” <https://www.google.com/search?q=role+of+lis+in+nonacademic+libraries&ie=utf-8&oe=utf-8&client=firefox-b>
- [7]. Goswami, S. and Biswas, P. (2011). Role of libraries and LIS professionals on open educational resources in modern information era. Vol. 1, no. Issue. 1, Sep. 2011.
- [8]. Horava, T. and Curran, B. (2012). The Importance of Case Studies for LIS Education. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 2012.
- [9]. Kingsley DA and Kennan MA (2015) *Open access: The whipping boy for problems in scholarly publishing. Communications of the Association for Information Systems*; 37 (14), <http://aisel.aisnet.org/cais/vol37/iss1/14>
- [10]. Liaising Outside the Box," *Collaborative Librarianship*: Vol. 9 : Iss. 2 , Article 9, available at: <https://digitalcommons.du.edu/collaborativelibrarianship/vol9/iss2/9>
- [11]. Muralidhar, D. and Rao K. M. (2013). Development of Public Libraries through Public-private Partnership in India: Issues and Challenges, *DESIDOC Journal of Library & Information Technology*., Vol. 33, No. 1, p. 21–24, Jan. 2013.
- [12]. National Literacy Trust. (2013) Children’s on-screen reading overtakes reading in print, http://www.literacytrust.org.uk/media/5371_children_s_on-screen_reading_overtakes_reading_in_print
- [13]. Perrault, A.H., Gregory, V.L. and Carey, J.O. (2002). The integration of assessment of student learning outcomes with teaching effectiveness. *Journal of Education for Library and Information Science*, Vol. 43 No. 4, pp. 270-82.
- [14]. Research Councils UK. (2015) Common principles on data management, <http://www.rcuk.ac.uk/research/datapolicy/>
- [15]. Sahu, A. K., Goswami, N. G. and Choudhury, B. K. (2014). Information Needs of Library Users of Selective Metallurgical Institutions in Jharkhand. *DESIDOC Journal of Library & Information Technology*, Vol 34, No 1, p.. 3–10, Jan. 2014.
- [16]. SCONUL. (June 2015) Changing trends in loans, visits & the use of e-books, <http://www.sconul.ac.uk/sites/default/files/documents/Analysis%20Loans%20ebooks%20visits%20June%202015.pdf>
- [17]. Siddamallaiiah, H.S. and Kemparaj, T.D. (2006). Dynamics of continued curriculum development for LIS, in Karisiddappa, C.R. and Kumar, B.D. (Eds), *Building Curriculum with a Difference: A Vision for LIS Education in the 21st Century*. Proceedings of the 23rd IATLIS National Conference, 23-25 November, Patiala, IATLIS, Dharwad, pp. 460-8.
- [18]. Singh, D. (1991), A comparative study of career advancement of library professionals in university libraries in Punjab, Haryana, Madhya Pradesh and Uttar Pradesh. Delhi University.
- [19]. Tait E et al. (2016) Libraries for the future: the role of IT utilities in the transformation of academic libraries. *Palgrave Communications*. 2:16070 doi: 10.1057/palcomms.2016.70.
- [20]. Tchoba, J. B. and Price J. A. (1993), “Industrial Information Service Managers: Expectations of, and Support of, the Educational Process. *Library Trends*, Vol. 42, No. 2, p. 249–56, 1993.
- [21]. Varalakshmi, R.S.R. (2006). Educating 21st Century LIS Professionals—Needs and Expectations: A Survey of Indian LIS Professionals and Alumni. *Journal of Education for Library and Information Science*, Vol. 47, No. 3, Summer, 2006, pp. 181-199
- [22]. Wainwright, Amy and Davidson, Chris (2017) "Academic Libraries and Non-Academic Departments: A Survey and Case Studies on
- [22]. Walters WH (2013) *E-books in academic libraries: challenges for acquisition and collection management, portal. Libraries and the Academy*; 13 (2): 187–211
- [23]. Wijetunge, P. and Willson, J. (1998). Perceptions of Library and Information Science Education and Training in Sri Lanka.